

Effect of Carbon and Nitrogen Sources on Growth and Luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* (Bull.) P. Karst.

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ABSTRACT

The effect of carbon and nitrogen compounds was evaluated on the growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* (Bulliard ex Fr.) P. Karst. Out of the ten carbon sources tested D (+) raffinose was found to be best carbon source for the luminescence whereas starch supported the maximum mycelial growth in liquid as well as on solid medium. The fungus exhibited nil growth with L (-) sorbose. Among inorganic nitrogen sources, the fungus utilized potassium nitrate as best nitrogen source for maximum biomass production and luminescence in the liquid medium. However, on solid medium maximum biomass production and luminescence was observed with peptone and ammonium acetate, respectively. Among organic nitrogen sources, maximum biomass production was observed in L-cystine, whereas maximum luminescence was observed in L-histidine HCl in liquid medium. On solid medium, the fungus exhibited maximum luminescence with L-histidine HCl and mycelial growth with DL-threonine.

Keywords: Luminescence, *Panellus stipticus*, D (+) raffinose, potassium nitrate, ammonium acetate, L-histidine HCl.

INTRODUCTION

The bioluminescence is the emission of visible light by living organisms mediated by enzyme-catalyzed (luciferase) reaction of molecular oxygen with a substrate (luciferin). Bioluminescent systems are quite diverse and widely distributed in nature, for example bacteria, fungi, algae, worms, cypridina, jellyfish, firefly, insects, etc. [1, 2, 3]. The process of light emission could be continuous (bacteria and fungi) or may occur in brief flashes (firefly and dinoflagellates) and it may be intracellular (bacteria, fungi, firefly) or extracellular with the chemical compounds in the medium in which the reaction occurs (jellyfish). The bioluminescence in fungi occurs intracellularly and has been noted at spore level [2, 4, 5]. The energy in photon can vary with the frequency (color) of light. Different types of substrate (luciferins) in organisms produce different colors. Marine organisms emit blue light, jellyfish emit green, fireflies emit greenish-yellow, railroad worms emit red and fungi emit bluish-green light.

Relatively little research has been carried out on naturally bioluminescent fungi to know the effect of different macro and micro-nutrients on growth, reproduction and luminescence [2,6]. Recently it has been found that bioluminescence response of *Armillaria mellea* (Vahl ex Fr.) Karst. declined in high concentration of Cu whereas it remained unaffected by the varied concentration of Ni [7]. This indicates a possible use of luminescent fungi like *P. stipticus* as bioindicators/biosensors of individual trace elements. However, little work has been done in this direction so far. The possible use of these organisms as biosensor/bioindicator can only be accomplished

by initiating physiological studies to know their behavior fully on a reproducible culture media.

In light of the above mentioned fact, studies have been initiated to find out the optimum physiological requirements for the growth and luminescence of *P. stipticus* for its use as bio-indicator/biosensor. The objective of this communication was to study the effect of carbon sources on the mycelial growth and luminescence of *P. stipticus*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material:

The pure cultures of *P. stipticus* were maintained on malt yeast agar medium (malt extract 3g, yeast extract 3g, peptone 5g, glucose 10g, agar 20g in distilled water to make 1 L). For all experiments, the fungus was sub-cultured onto the above mentioned medium and stored for up to one month at $\pm 4^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the refrigerator.

Methods:

The glucose-peptone medium was used for all the experiments as it was found to be best medium for growth and luminescence [8]. The fungus was incubated *in vitro* on solid and liquid basal medium at optimum temperature (24°C), pH (4.0) and days of incubation (13) for determining the optimum carbon and nitrogen sources requirement for growth and luminescence. The basal medium was solidified with 2% agar-agar (A/R) in case of solid medium experiments.

Effect of carbon sources:

The glucose of the glucose-peptone medium was substituted singly by each of the carbon compounds so as to provide

0.333g/l of carbon - a substituent of glucose (10g/l) in the basal medium. The basal medium without carbon source was adjusted to optimum pH (4.0). Initial pH of the separate solutions of each carbon compound was adjusted to 7.0 in order to avoid any breakdown of carbohydrates during autoclaving. The two solutions were then separately autoclaved at 15 lbs psi steam pressure for 15 minutes. These were then mixed together aseptically and proportionately to get the normal strength of the basal medium. The basal medium was again adjusted to its specific pH (4.0) with sterilized solutions of 1N KOH and 1N HCl and checked over P/L Philips precision instrument PR 9045 M. Control without additional carbon source was run in parallel.

Effect of Inorganic and Organic nitrogen sources:

The effect of different nitrogen sources was evaluated replacing the peptone by different amino acids and inorganic nitrogen compounds (2.0 g/l) at optimum conditions i.e. at 24°C and pH 4.0 in raffinose supplemented basal medium for 13 days of incubation. The basal medium without nitrogen source was adjusted to optimum pH (4.0). Initial pH of the separate solutions of each nitrogen compound was adjusted to 7.0 in order to avoid any breakdown of any amino acid during autoclaving. The two solutions were then separately autoclaved at 15lbs psi steam pressure for 15 minutes. These were then mixed together aseptically and proportionately to get the normal strength of the basal medium. The basal medium was again adjusted to its specific pH (4.0) with sterilized solutions of 1N KOH and 1N HCl and checked over P/L Philips precision instrument PR 9045 M. Control without additional nitrogen source was run in parallel.

Twenty five ml of the basal medium were then apportioned aseptically in each 100 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask. Each flask was seeded with one ml of the standardized mycelial suspension and incubated. For solid medium experiments, a mycelial disc was seeded in 50 ml of the medium (solidified) in 250 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask. Three replicates were kept for each variable.

Determination of mycelial dry weight and final pH:

At the end of each experiment, the mycelium of each replicate was filtered through a goosch crucible of known weight (containing a disc of Whatman filter paper No.1). The mycelium was dried at 60°C in a hot air oven to a constant weight and the weight of the individual replicate was recorded. The final pH of the culture filtrate of the individual replicate was checked over Philips precision instrument PR 9045 M and recorded.

Bioluminescence measurement:

Bioluminescence was measured by using a TD 20/20 (Version 2.2) luminometer with the sensitivity set at 35% and recorded as relative light units (RLU). All bioluminescence measurements were done at the same time.

Statistical analysis of the data:

The data on growth of all the experiments were analyzed statistically with respect to dry weight of the mycelium of individual replicate with variables by applying one-way Anova in terms of significance and non-significance of the data. The significance is denoted by statistical error (S.E.) and Statistical error of difference (S.Ed.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this experiment, a comparative account of growth (average mycelial dry weight – mg) and luminescence was studied with different carbon and nitrogen compounds. The study revealed that the optimum luminescence was obtained with D (+) raffinose followed by D (+) glucose and D (-) fructose in liquid medium. The maximum mycelial dry weight was obtained with starch followed by D (-) fructose, sucrose and pectin (Fig. 1a). In utilizing D (+) raffinose, this fungus resembles *Morchella esculenta* [9], *Lentinus edodes* [10] and *Ustilago esculenta* [11]. This however, differs from *Calvatia* spp. for which, raffinose is a poor source of carbon [12]. Airth and Foerster, [13] found that glucose was best source for growth and luminescence of *Collybia velutipes* whereas Bermudes *et al.*, [14] used glucose, maltose, trehalose, cellobiose, pectin or other complex carbon sources for growth and luminescence of *P. stipticus* and observed that pectin gave maximum luminescence whereas fructose gave maximum growth. They did not use raffinose which gives maximum luminescence in our experiments. The fungus showed poor or nil growth with L (-) sorbose in liquid as well as on solid medium. However, it showed maximum mycelial growth with starch and pectin followed by fructose and sucrose on solid medium and the highest luminescence was observed with raffinose followed by starch and sucrose (Figs 1b).

Fig. 1a Growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* with different carbon compounds in liquid medium at 24°C and pH 4.0 after 13 days of incubation.

The fungus exhibited maximum mycelial dry weight with potassium nitrate in liquid media followed by ammonium acetate, ammonium nitrate and ammonium chloride whereas, maximum luminescence was observed with potassium nitrate followed by ammonium oxalate and ammonium chloride in liquid medium (Fig. 2a). It gave maximum luminescence with ammonium acetate followed by ammonium sulphate, potassium nitrate and peptone on solid medium and maximum mycelial growth with peptone followed by sodium nitrate, ammonium acetate and ammonium sulphate (Fig. 2b). The fungus exhibited maximum luminescence with L-histidine HCl followed by proline, phenylalanine and L-cystine in liquid medium whereas, maximum biomass production was observed in L-cystine followed by DL-aspartic acid and L-histidine HCl (Fig. 3a).

Fig. 1b Growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* with different carbon compounds on solid medium at 24°C and pH 4.0 after 13 days of incubation.

On solid medium, the fungus exhibited maximum luminescence with L-histidine HCl followed by proline and L-tyrosine. However, maximum mycelial growth was observed with DL-threonine followed by proline, L-arginine HCl and lysine HCl (Fig. 3b). Bermudes *et al.*, [14] studied the effect of various nitrogen sources on luminescence and growth of *Panellus stipticus* and found that ammonium and L-asparagine were preferred substrata. Airth and Foerster, [13] previously reported that L-aspartic acid exhibits maximum luminescence for *C. velutipes* and Wassink, [6] found that L-asparagine shows optimum luminescence for *P. stipticus*.

Fig. 2a Growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* with different inorganic nitrogen compounds in liquid medium at 24°C and pH 4.0 after 13 days of incubation.

Fig. 2b Growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* with different inorganic nitrogen compounds on solid medium at 24°C and pH 4.0 after 13 days of incubation.

CONCLUSIONS

Physiological studies pertaining to carbon and nitrogen sources requirements have been carried out on the luminescent fungus *P. stipticus* for its evaluation as a test organism for biosensor. Pure cultures of *P. stipticus* have been maintained on malt yeast agar medium (malt extract 3g, yeast extract 3g, peptone 5g, glucose 10g, agar 20g in distilled water to make 1L) at $\pm 4^\circ\text{C}$ and revived after two months. Glucose-peptone medium containing g/l: Glucose 10.0, peptone 2.0, potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate 1.0, magnesium sulphate 0.5, was used for the studies on the luminescence of *P. stipticus* in the experiments.

Fig. 3a Growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* with different organic nitrogen compounds in liquid medium at 24°C and pH 4.0 after 13 days of incubation.

Fig. 3b Growth and luminescence of *Panellus stipticus* with different organic nitrogen compounds on solid medium at 24°C and pH 4.0 after 13 days of incubation.

The best carbon source for the luminescence of the fungus is D (+) raffinose in liquid as well as on solid medium. Among inorganic and organic nitrogen sources, *P. stipticus* utilizes L-histidine HCl as best nitrogen source for maximum luminescence in liquid as well as on solid medium.

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